

Immersive Technologies for Engineering Education: A Virtual Reality Experience at the UPTC Geology Museum.

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Abstract

The integration of Virtual Reality (VR) in engineering education emerges as a strategy to contribute to challenges such as accessibility, student participation, and modernization of teaching-learning methodologies. This study focuses on designing and implementing immersive virtual environments in the Geology Museum of the Universidad Pedagógica y Tecnológica de Colombia UPTC, located in Sogamoso, Boyacá—surrounded by rich evidence of geological events and heritage places. The main objective of this work is to develop dynamic and inclusive educational experiences that close youngsters and kids to geology and earth science engineering programs.

This research focuses on two main questions: How do immersive technologies impact the learning of geological and engineering issues? And how can a multidimensional design optimize the knowledge acquisition process in these fields? Using VR, exploring detailed geological models, participating in interactive educational activities, and performing virtual tours are facilitated for on-site and remote users seeking to strengthen retention and conceptual understanding.

Our project follows a methodology composed of three main stages: development, implementation, and evaluation of VR-based learning modules. The project includes the creation of immersive environments that represent geological phenomena and present engineering practices, including resource exploration, physical characteristics, and behavior of geological materials. The project is currently in its second stage, focused on refining functionality and integrating user feedback to improve interaction and learning experience.

Preliminary results suggest that VR-mediated learning environments improve the understanding of complex geological concepts while promoting the appreciation of cultural heritage. Besides enhancing the learning experience among users, the strategic implementation of VR as a pedagogical tool can potentially position the museum as a benchmark in incorporating technological innovation for promoting sustainable tourism and scientific education. Our approach aims to benefit local academic and tourist communities and to serve as a replicable model for other institutions at national and international levels.

Keywords: Virtual Reality; Geology Education; Immersive Learning; Engineering Education; Innovation.

1 Introduction

Engineering education in the 21st century faces a dual challenge: the demand for high-quality conceptual understanding and the need to adapt to the digital transformation of learning environments. Virtual Reality (VR), as part of the broader family of immersive technologies, emerges as a powerful pedagogical innovation capable of reshaping how scientific and engineering content is taught and learned. Specifically, VR introduces experiential learning opportunities that address the spatial-temporal complexities, abstract concepts, and access limitations traditionally associated with fields such as geological engineering.

A growing body of literature demonstrates that immersive technologies foster deeper engagement, enhance knowledge retention, and improve learner satisfaction (Radianti et al., 2020). These benefits are rooted in VR's ability to provide multisensory, interactive, and contextualized experiences that simulate real-world scenarios. In geology education, this capacity becomes particularly relevant, as geological phenomena often occur over vast timeframes and in environments that are difficult to access physically, such as deep-sea trenches, volcanoes, or fossil beds (Bonali et al., 2021).

The theoretical foundations of immersive learning environments stem from constructivist learning theory, which emphasizes knowledge construction through active engagement and situated cognition. VR offers a “learning-by-being” experience, allowing learners to internalize content through embodied interaction rather than passive reception (Bricken, 1991). In this sense, immersive technologies enable learners to not only visualize but also manipulate complex models, fostering metacognitive awareness and spatial reasoning skills (le Roux et al., 2021)

From a cognitive load perspective, VR has been shown to facilitate the organization of information by reducing extraneous load and enhancing germane load through interactive exploration (Mayer, 2019). This aligns with the Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning (CTML), which posits that learning improves when learners can integrate words and images meaningfully (Mayer, 2009). VR extends this principle by offering dynamic, manipulable 3D environments that allow for richer sensory integration and experiential cognition.

Moreover, studies on the impact of immersive virtual environments in STEM education highlight the importance of presence—the psychological sense of “being there”—in mediating learning outcomes. Makransky and Mayer (2022) argue that presence enhances motivation and curiosity, two essential elements for inquiry-based learning and scientific thinking. This motivational boost is especially critical in engineering disciplines, where abstract concepts often pose barriers to student engagement (Mayer, 2009).

Beyond cognitive gains, immersive learning environments support inclusive education by addressing accessibility issues in both geographic and cognitive terms. Learners from underserved communities, rural areas, or institutions lacking physical resources can benefit from virtual access to otherwise unreachable geological phenomena. Additionally, students with different learning preferences—visual, kinesthetic, or experiential—find in VR a platform that caters to multimodal learning (Jensen & Konradsen, 2018).

Within this pedagogical and technological landscape, the UPTC Geology Museum in Sogamoso, Boyacá, offers an ideal setting to explore how VR can transform geological and engineering education. Situated in a region of rich geological diversity, the museum acts as both a scientific repository and an educational hub. However, like many educational institutions, it faces limitations in terms of outreach, interactivity, and curriculum integration. The introduction of immersive VR experiences at the museum is intended to bridge these gaps by providing learners with interactive, context-rich simulations based on real geological data and paleontological records.

This project also aligns with global educational frameworks that emphasize the integration of digital tools to enhance quality and equity. The UNESCO (2021) Recommendation on Open Science advocates for the use of inclusive and innovative technologies to democratize access to knowledge and promote scientific citizenship. By digitizing and virtualizing geological heritage, institutions like UPTC can contribute to cultural preservation while fostering public engagement in science (UNESCO, 2021).

The present study focuses on the design, implementation, and evaluation of immersive educational modules using virtual reality (VR), with a specific emphasis on three core areas: fossils, sedimentary formations, and mineralogy. These topics were selected based on their relevance to regional heritage and their didactic potential to illustrate key geological processes. The virtual environments were developed with scientific rigor, integrating data from the Colombian Geological Survey, academic publications, and field mapping.

Two research questions guide the educational experience:

1. **How do immersive technologies impact the learning of geological and engineering issues?**
2. **How can a multidimensional design optimize the knowledge acquisition process in these fields?**

By addressing these questions, the paper aims to contribute to the theoretical and practical understanding of VR as a transformative tool in engineering education. The project's scope goes beyond technological experimentation; it is an effort to create a replicable, scalable, and inclusive model that combines scientific rigor, pedagogical innovation, and regional relevance.

In summary, this initiative integrates theoretical principles of constructivism, multimedia learning, and cognitive psychology with practical implementation in a real educational context. It seeks to validate the hypothesis that immersive technologies, when applied through a multidimensional design, can significantly enhance the learning process in complex scientific fields such as geology and engineering.

2 Methodology

This study adopted a qualitative exploratory methodology grounded in participatory and experiential learning principles to design, implement, and evaluate immersive Virtual Reality (VR) educational modules in geology and engineering contexts. The methodological framework was structured into three interrelated phases—design of immersive environments, implementation of educational modules, and impact evaluation—each developed through interdisciplinary collaboration between geology and systems engineering students, museum professionals, and university faculty. Drawing on the constructivist paradigm and experiential learning theory (Bricken, 1991; Makransky & Mayer, 2022), the project sought to foster user-centered, interactive experiences that enhance conceptual understanding and engagement. Rather than applying rigid experimental controls, the methodology emphasized authenticity, contextual relevance, and iterative refinement based on user feedback and direct observation. This approach allowed the research team to continuously adapt the technical and pedagogical elements of the VR environments to meet the needs of diverse educational audiences, including schoolchildren, university students, and museum visitors. The project also aligned with recommendations for immersive learning evaluation, prioritizing navigability, didactic effectiveness, and cognitive-emotional responses (Merchant et al., 2014; Pellas et al., 2021). Each phase of the methodology contributed to building a comprehensive understanding of how immersive technologies can support learning in geosciences while promoting interdisciplinary collaboration and the appropriation of local scientific heritage.

2.1 Design of Immersive Environments

The design phase was rooted in experiential learning principles, aiming to foster authentic, learner-centered engagement with geological content. The collaborative development team included geology students and museum staff—acting as both scientific experts and digital artists—who conceptualized the environments based on real fossil evidence. Systems engineering students then translated these proposals into immersive virtual environments using Blender for 3D modeling and Unity for interaction design.

The models were inspired by naturally occurring fossils and mineral formations found in Boyacá, Colombia. These elements were selected for their scientific relevance and cultural value, particularly specimens from regions like Villa de Leyva. Although photogrammetry and laser scanning were not used, fossil documentation and field-based sketching provided a solid foundation for accurately rendering textures, morphologies, and spatial arrangements.

Three thematic environments were developed: Fossils, Sedimentary Formations, and Mineralogy (Ruiz-Sánchez, Benavent San Cornelio, & Lázaro Calatayud, 2021). Each environment offers two levels of complexity—basic and advanced—catering to children, general audiences, and students at secondary and university levels. The design aligned with the curricular competencies of geology and systems engineering programs, while encouraging interdisciplinary collaboration. Based on these themes, three-dimensional scenarios were

developed using specialized software (Blender¹ and Unity²), incorporating real data obtained from cartography, laser scanning, and photogrammetry (Liu et al., 2017).

Interaction within these environments is primarily exploratory, allowing users to navigate at their own pace through virtual landscapes, examine artifacts, and engage with visual cues. Key features include immersive scene transitions, contextual audio guides, and intuitive controls for object manipulation. Gamified elements, such as discovery badges and knowledge pop-ups, were integrated to promote engagement without disrupting the educational flow.

The environments were also designed to be inclusive, with clear visual hierarchies and accessible navigation interfaces. This phase emphasized scientific accuracy, usability, and didactic coherence, ensuring that learners not only observe but also experience geological concepts in a virtual yet contextually grounded setting.

2.2 Implementation of Educational Modules

The educational modules were implemented using Meta Quest 2 and Quest 3 headsets, providing a fully immersive, wireless VR experience. The modules were deployed in two main contexts: structured pilot sessions with schoolchildren and an open demonstration during the "Museum's Night" academic event. In total, six groups of 15 children and one group of 20 university participants interacted with the virtual environments, offering diverse feedback for iterative improvement.

The immersive experiences were designed to support exploratory learning, allowing users to freely navigate 3D environments representing fossils, sedimentary layers, and mineralogical specimens. Though no formal tasks were assigned during the sessions, participants engaged spontaneously with the virtual content, triggering cognitive reflection and curiosity—especially among younger users. These results are consistent with findings from Merchant et al. (2014), who note that interactive VR fosters learner autonomy and deepened engagement.

Modules were built using Unity and guided by the ADDIE model (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, Evaluation), focusing on accessibility, usability, and pedagogical relevance (Pellas et al., 2021). Real-time feedback from participants, especially children, highlighted aesthetic aspects—such as requests for brighter colors and enhanced environmental sounds—that contributed to improved immersion and engagement. Some students also reported dizziness, a common challenge in immersive VR that the team is currently addressing through interface adjustments.

Importantly, museum staff validated the realism and scientific accuracy of the VR representations. Their feedback ensured alignment with real fossil specimens and supported the module's credibility as an educational tool. Students noted that the VR environments facilitated a better understanding of complex processes such as fossilization, reinforcing the potential of immersive learning to enhance conceptual clarity in geoscience education (Makransky & Mayer, 2022).

2.3 Impact Evaluation

The impact of the VR modules was evaluated through participant observation and oral feedback, focusing on three key dimensions: navigability, didactic experience, and conceptual understanding. Rather than relying on formal surveys or interviews, the research team employed a qualitative approach, consistent with exploratory methodologies recommended for immersive learning environments (Merchant et al., 2014; Pellas et al., 2021).

¹ <https://www.blender.org/>

² <https://unity.com/>

Observation was conducted during both school visits and university-level sessions. In the case of university students, the experience was preceded by a traditional lecture on fossilization and geological environments. After the VR session, participants reported a deeper and faster understanding of the subject matter compared to the lecture format alone—highlighting VR’s potential to enhance cognitive efficiency and engagement, as suggested by Makransky and Mayer (2022). Students could articulate, in their own words, the physiological traits of organisms and their surrounding ecosystems, demonstrating the integration of visual and conceptual information.

Among schoolchildren, interactions were characterized by spontaneous exploration and curiosity. Children were able to identify animals, plants, and geographical features, linking virtual elements to their prior knowledge and emotional reactions. The depth of exploration and expressed enthusiasm reflected the high motivational value of the experience—an outcome aligned with findings by Radianti et al. (2020) on immersive learning’s capacity to support sustained engagement.

To systematize the observed learning outcomes, a rubric was used to assess discourse clarity and emotional association with the content. Documentation of oral reflections and behavior allowed the team to identify areas for improvement, such as enhancing visual cues and spatial orientation. This iterative feedback—particularly from the museum staff—helped refine the technical design and strengthen the pedagogical coherence of the environments.

3 Results

The implementation of immersive Virtual Reality (VR) modules at the UPTC Geology Museum yielded multifaceted outcomes across four key dimensions: iterative design advancements, user engagement and usability, contextual relevance, and cognitive gains. These results underscore the efficacy of VR as a pedagogical tool in geoscience education, aligning with contemporary research on immersive learning environments.

3.1 Iterative Design Advancements in Geological Learning

The development process of the VR modules—encompassing Fossils, Sedimentary Formations, and Mineralogy—was characterized by iterative refinement informed by interdisciplinary collaboration. Geology students and museum professionals provided scientific accuracy, while systems engineering students translated these insights into interactive 3D environments using Unity and Blender.

Initial prototypes underwent multiple revisions based on feedback from pilot sessions. Adjustments included enhancing visual fidelity, optimizing navigation controls, and integrating ambient audio to simulate real-world geological settings. These refinements aimed to create an immersive experience that facilitates experiential learning, a pedagogical approach supported by Makransky and Mayer (2022), who emphasize the importance of immersive environments in promoting deep learning through active engagement.

3.2 User Engagement and Usability Observations

User interactions with the VR modules revealed distinct engagement patterns among different age groups. Schoolchildren exhibited exploratory behavior, navigating the virtual environments with curiosity and enthusiasm. They identified various geological features and provided spontaneous feedback on aspects such as color schemes and sound effects, indicating a high level of immersion and emotional connection to the content.

University students, who had prior exposure to traditional lectures on similar topics, reported that the VR experience enhanced their understanding of complex geological processes. They noted that the immersive

nature of the modules facilitated a more intuitive grasp of concepts like fossilization and stratigraphy. This observation aligns with findings by Merchant et al. (2014), who conducted a meta-analysis demonstrating that VR-based instruction significantly improves student learning outcomes compared to traditional methods.

However, some users reported experiencing dizziness during the VR sessions, highlighting the need for careful consideration of user comfort in immersive environments. Addressing such issues is crucial for optimizing the usability of VR applications in educational settings.

3.3 Contextual Relevance and Integration of Local Heritage

The VR modules were designed to reflect the geological heritage of the Boyacá region, incorporating digital representations of local fossil specimens and geological formations. This contextualization fostered a sense of connection among users, particularly schoolchildren, who recognized familiar elements within the virtual environments.

The inclusion of region-specific content not only enhanced engagement but also facilitated the appropriation of scientific knowledge within a cultural framework. This approach aligns with the principles outlined by Radianti et al. (2020), who emphasize the importance of contextual relevance in immersive learning experiences to foster a deeper understanding and retention of information.

3.4 Cognitive Gains and Knowledge Appropriation

Observational data and oral feedback indicated that the VR modules effectively supported the development of conceptual understanding among users. Schoolchildren articulated their experiences using age-appropriate language, demonstrating an ability to relate virtual observations to real-world geological phenomena.

University students exhibited a more sophisticated discourse, employing technical terminology to describe processes such as sedimentation and fossilization. This progression in cognitive engagement underscores the potential of VR to facilitate knowledge construction across different educational levels.

Additionally, younger visitors showed notable enthusiasm while interacting with virtual representations of dinosaurs, especially local species such as *Sachicasaurus vitae* (Páramo-Fonseca et al., 2018) and *Monquirasaurus boyacensis* (Noè y Gómez-Pérez, 2022). These activities not only sparked scientific curiosity but also prompted spontaneous discussions on morphology, evolution, and the historical memory associated with the region's paleontological heritage—demonstrating a multiplier effect in fostering scientific citizenship.

The positive impact of immersive learning on cognitive outcomes is further corroborated by Makransky and Mayer (2022), who found that VR-based instruction enhances learners' ability to comprehend and retain complex information by providing interactive and engaging experiences.

4 Concluding Remark

The implementation of immersive Virtual Reality (VR) modules at the Universidad Pedagógica y Tecnológica de Colombia's (UPTC) Geology Museum stands as a compelling case of how educational innovation, rooted in local heritage and global pedagogical theory, can transform geoscience and engineering education. The results of this study confirm that immersive learning environments—when grounded in experiential learning principles and developed through interdisciplinary collaboration—can foster deep conceptual understanding, emotional engagement, and knowledge appropriation among diverse learner populations.

One of the most significant outcomes of this project is the successful integration of VR into real-world geological learning contexts, offering a dynamic alternative to traditional lectures and textbook-based instruction. By simulating fossil beds, sediment layers, and mineral formations, the modules provide a vivid, multisensory experience that makes abstract or inaccessible phenomena tangible and relevant. This aligns with Makransky and Mayer's (2022) findings that immersive learning enhances comprehension and retention through presence and interactivity, which are central to multimedia learning theory.

The impact of the VR environments was particularly evident when comparing student performance and feedback before and after experiencing the modules. While conventional teaching methods offer a foundation in theory, VR facilitates faster and more intuitive assimilation of complex geological concepts. University students noted that the VR modules not only reinforced but also expanded their understanding, helping them visualize and manipulate representations of geological processes in ways not possible in the physical classroom. These observations reinforce prior research by Merchant et al. (2014), which found that immersive technologies support superior learning outcomes, especially in STEM disciplines.

Just as importantly, the exploratory engagement observed among schoolchildren demonstrated the platform's ability to democratize access to scientific content. The absence of formal assessments in the experience allowed for unstructured curiosity, leading children to ask questions spontaneously, suggest improvements, and express excitement about what they were learning. Their ability to recognize and discuss prehistoric life forms, environmental features, and even local geographic markers indicates a high level of connection to the content. This level of interaction mirrors what Radianti et al. (2020) describe as "transformational learning," where immersive technologies foster deep emotional and cognitive involvement that can translate into long-term interest and understanding.

Another core strength of the project is its emphasis on local contextualization. By incorporating real fossils from the Boyacá region, including iconic species such as *Sachicasaurus vitae* and *Monquirasaurus boyacensis*, the VR environments became more than just simulations—they became digital extensions of cultural and scientific heritage. This place-based approach increases learner motivation and community relevance, aligning with UNESCO's (2021) calls for the use of digital technologies to preserve and disseminate knowledge of natural and cultural significance.

Incorporating regional content not only promotes heritage recognition but also strengthens learners' sense of belonging and ownership of knowledge. For instance, children were not merely passive users; they became co-creators in the learning experience by suggesting color schemes, sound effects, and navigational features. Their feedback directly contributed to the refinement of the modules, making the project a living example of participatory design. This feedback loop, in turn, reinforces the democratic potential of VR in educational design, as outlined in constructivist learning frameworks.

Institutionally, the project has elevated the role of the UPTC Geology Museum, transforming it into a hybrid educational and outreach platform. The museum's VR modules offer a flexible learning resource that can be adapted to various academic levels—from elementary to higher education—and serve both formal and informal education. This hybrid capacity is particularly important in regions where access to geological field sites may be limited due to financial, geographic, or logistical constraints. VR mitigates these barriers by providing safe, repeatable, and inclusive access to otherwise difficult-to-reach geological phenomena.

Furthermore, the interdisciplinary nature of the project has enhanced academic collaboration within the university. Geology students, museum staff, and systems engineering students worked together across disciplines to design, develop, and test the modules. This process not only enriched the quality of the final product but also modeled the kind of collaborative problem-solving that is increasingly expected in 21st-

century professional environments. The alignment with curricular standards in both geology and systems engineering programs ensured that the modules met educational objectives while encouraging innovation in instructional design.

Looking ahead, the project's success presents multiple opportunities for scalability and replication. The modular nature of the VR environments allows for the addition of new content areas, such as volcanology, hydrology, or structural geology, as well as the integration of multilingual interfaces and accessibility features for users with disabilities. Moreover, partnerships with other educational institutions and museums could extend the reach of the project, making it a national or even international model for immersive science education.

To ensure long-term sustainability, future work will focus on four strategic areas. First, improving user experience by addressing physical discomfort (e.g., dizziness), optimizing spatial orientation, and refining interface ergonomics. Second, integrating formative and summative assessment tools within the VR modules to quantitatively measure learning outcomes, skill development, and user satisfaction. Third, exploring the integration of artificial intelligence and adaptive learning to personalize the learning journey based on user behavior. And fourth, developing partnerships with government and educational agencies to align with public policy objectives on digital education, equity, and scientific literacy.

Finally, this initiative contributes to broader academic discourse on the intersection of technology, culture, and pedagogy. It shows that immersive technologies are not just tools for simulation—they are platforms for inclusive knowledge construction, cultural engagement, and interdisciplinary dialogue. The experience at UPTC reflects a model where local heritage, academic excellence, and technological innovation converge to build an education system that is both globally informed and locally grounded.

In conclusion, the immersive VR project developed at the UPTC Geology Museum affirms the educational value of virtual environments in facilitating deep, engaging, and inclusive learning. It lays the foundation for replicable strategies in higher and engineering education that integrate digital innovation with place-based learning and cultural heritage. More than a technological endeavor, this project is a blueprint for the future of education—one that is interactive, collaborative, and meaningfully connected to the world in which learners live.

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